

Machine Learning for heat radiation modeling of bi- and polydisperse particle systems including walls

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ABSTRACT

We investigated the ability of four popular Machine Learning methods i.e., Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), Random Forest-based regressors (RFRs), Extreme Gradient Boosting-based regressors (XGBs), and stacked ensembles of DNNs, to model the radiative heat transfer based on view factors in bi- and polydisperse particle beds including walls. Before training and analyzing the predictive capability of each method, an adjustment of markers used in monodisperse systems, as well as an evaluation of new markers was performed. On the basis of our dataset that considers a wide range of particle radii ratios, system sizes, particle volume fractions, as well as different particle-species volume fractions, we found that (i) the addition of particle size information allows the transition from monodisperse to bi- and polydisperse beds, and (ii) the addition of particle volume fraction information as the fourth marker leads to very accurate predictions. In terms of the overall performance, DNNs and RFRs should be preferred compared to the other two options. For particle–particle view factors, DNN and RFR are on par, while for particle–wall the RFR is superior. We demonstrate that DNNs and RFRs can be built to meet or even exceed the prediction quality standards achieved in a monodisperse system.

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1. Introduction

Many high temperature processes, where radiation is a significant or the dominant heat transfer mechanism, feature polydispersity, e.g., fluidized (Capecelatro & Desjardins, 2013; Tien, 1988) respectively packed beds (Gupta et al., 2002), rotary kilns (Krause et al., 2015), or selective laser sintering (Tran & Lo, 2018). A separate experimental observation of thermal radiation is very complex and is therefore hardly ever carried out. This is especially true for systems containing polydisperse particles. Consequently, radiative heat transfer is only investigated as part of the total heat transfer in an experiment. Therefore, experimentally-driven investigations often yield correlations (Tran & Lo, 2018; Zhou et al., 2009) that describe the total heat transfer rate rather than each contribution to this rate.

For the processes mentioned above, the Discrete Element Method (DEM) (Emady et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2016, 2018a; Yohannes et al., 2016), Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) (De

Beer et al., 2017; Wehinger, 2019), a combination of both CFD-DEM (Krause et al., 2015; Oschmann & Kruggel-Emden, 2018; Wu et al., 2017, 2018b), and the Two-Fluid Model (TFM) (Agrawal et al., 2013) can be used for a numerical description. Therefore, these more advanced simulation tools offer some advantages over an experimental approach. CFD and TFM are usually applied when the surrounding media contributes to the heat transfer. In these situations, both methods rely on solving the radiative transfer equation (RTE) (Modest, 2003). The focus of the present work is on systems with no or negligible media involvement, so the solution of the RTE is not discussed further.

When no or negligible media contribution is present, the surface-to-surface radiation can be described based on geometric aspects between the surfaces. This geometrical relationship is described as a view factor (in literature also as “configuration factors”). Another possibility to describe the radiative heat transfer between surfaces is the Discrete Transfer Radiation Model (DTRM), which predicts the propagation of rays from the emitting surface through the simulation domain. DTRM uses a statistically significant (i.e., large) number of rays, typically generated based on Monte Carlo methods. This approach is called “Monte Carlo ray-tracing” (MCRT) and can be used for the direct calculation of the radiative

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heat transfer (Tran & Lo, 2018; Zhou et al., 2009) or to compute view factors between two surfaces (Tseng et al., 1992; Walker et al., 2010). The discrete origin of MCRT led to former use in DEM-based simulations (Amberger et al., 2013), which is unfortunately limited to a small number of particles due to the high computational cost. This initiated methods with reduced computational cost for view factor calculation (Feng & Han, 2012; Forgber & Radl, 2018; Liu et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2016), which unfortunately are still too computationally demanding for general use in DEM simulations. Mogthaderi et al. (Peng et al., 2020) recently reviewed DEM-based heat transfer modeling of thermal processes. They conclude that still significant work is required for modeling conduction and radiation in particle-laden systems. Methods such as simple correlations (Johnson et al., 2020; Krause et al., 2015; Pitso, 2011; Qi & Wright, 2018; Ruiz et al., 2019), which hardly require any computational effort, are tied to very specific setups and therefore limited in application (Peng et al., 2020; Van Antwerpen et al., 2010; Díaz-Heras et al., 2020).

The use of Machine Learning (ML) techniques is now well established in many branches of science. With a focus on heat transfer, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have been used by Annabattula et al. (Desu et al., 2019) to predict the effective thermal conductivity (ETC) of granular assemblies in the presence of a stagnant gas. Mahan et al. (Yarahmadi et al., 2020) predicted radiation distribution factors of grey diffuse surfaces. Kang et al. (Kang et al., 2019) also applied a DNN to predict the transmissivity in packed beds. It was based on the bed height, particle diameter, and particle surface emissivity. However, no view factors were calculated. Regarding view factor-based radiative heat transfer modeling Wu and Hao (Wu & Hao, 2020) and Wu et al. (Wu et al., 2020) used DNNs based on neighbor particle configurations between the emitting and absorbing particle for their prediction.

Separating radiation effects from total heat transfer is difficult, as mentioned at the outset, equal to separating wall effects from total heat transfer by radiation. De Beer et al. (De Beer et al., 2018) explicitly reviewed the near-wall region, concluding that no method correctly accounts for there. Studies that address the view factor, except for (Malinouski & Rabinovich, 2017), either consider it indirectly (Wu & Hao, 2020) or disregard particle wall effects (Wu et al., 2020). In summary, the radiative heat transfer between walls and particles is also often not modeled, or only modeled in a simplified form. This encouraged our previous publication (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), where we presented a DNN-based heat radiation model with low computational cost for particle–particle and particle–wall interactions. However, the investigated heat radiation configurations considered only mono-disperse particle systems.

Polydispersity is often a challenge of its own in modeling particulate multiphase flows (Marchisio & Fox, 2013), as well as in dry (i.e., single phase) particle flows (Berger & Hrenya, 2014). In terms of heat transfer and the ETC, polydispersity primarily impacts through the change of bed porosity (Chen et al., 2019; Gupta et al., 2002; Wu et al., 2018a, 2018b). The analytical solution for view factors involving (isolated) particles of different sizes is significantly different from the solution for particles of the same size (Feingold & Gupta, 1970; Felske, 1978). This suggests that polydispersity affects view factors in particle beds, and thus the radiative heat transfer rate. In view factor modeling, polydispersity was only considered by Malinouski and Rabinovich (Malinouski & Rabinovich, 2017). They used a ray-tracing method, similar to Feng and Han (Feng & Han, 2012), to calculate view factors between particles and between particles and walls in a polydisperse particle bed.

In our present contribution, we want to close the gap of heat radiation modeling of polydisperse systems, including

particle–wall radiation. We use ML techniques to create pre-trained models to overcome the computationally usually very expensive heat radiation models available in the literature.

1.1. Goals

The aim of our present contribution is to adapt our previously established model (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) to bi- & poly-disperse particle systems including particle–wall radiation. Therefore, the change of the existing input quantities of the neural network, i.e., the so-called markers, is systematically investigated. The addition of new markers, which include particle size information or variations of local and total particle volume fractions, will also be explored. Since we know from our previous study (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) that the total particle volume fraction has a significant impact on the view factor prediction quality, we also increase the generalization of our models by creating data sets that include a wide distribution of system and particle sizes, as well as different total particle volume fractions. In addition, we explore the capability of other ML algorithms such as Random Forests, Extreme Gradient Boosting machines, or ensembles of DNNs in terms of predictive power and speed.

1.2. Contents

This paper organizes as follows: We present the computational method in Section 2. The dataset creation and usage, the marker analysis and selection, are described in Section 3. Section 4 provides an overview and explanation of each Machine Learning-based view factor model. View factor predictions of each model are assessed in Section 5 and our main findings are summarized in Section 6. Fig. 1 summarizes the contents and gives an overview of the main steps of this contribution.

2. Computational methods

Although we will focus on a system of different-sized particles that are not moving, an accurate description of the particle movement is essential to generate realistic particle beds. Based on the DEM solver LIGGGHTS® (Kloss et al., 2012) the particle beds are created and then used to generate the input and the target data of the ML algorithms. The motion of spherical particles in the translational and rotational direction is described by:

$$m_{p,i} \frac{d\mathbf{v}_{p,i}}{dt} = \sum_j \left(\mathbf{F}_{cont,i-j}^n + \mathbf{F}_{cont,i-j}^t \right) + m_{p,i} \mathbf{g} \quad (1)$$

$$I_i \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} = \mathbf{T}_i \quad (2)$$

The mass of particle i is notated with $m_{p,i}$. $\mathbf{v}_{p,i}$ is the translational velocity of particle i . $\mathbf{F}_{cont,i-j}^n$ and $\mathbf{F}_{cont,i-j}^t$ are the normal and tangential contact forces. \mathbf{T}_i is the total torque (due to tangential contact forces) acting on particle i .

2.1. Monte Carlo ray-tracing

View factors determined with Monte Carlo ray-tracing (MCRT) are routinely used as ground truth for predictions in many studies available in the open literature (Forgber & Radl, 2018; Johnson et al., 2020; Tausendschön & Radl, 2021; Wu et al., 2020; Wu & Hao, 2020). In our present study, the MCRT algorithm of Walker et al. (Walker et al., 2010) is used. This tool (called RayFactor), calculates view factors between simple geometrical objects

Fig. 1. Overview of model development and usage.

(“primitives”) like planes, spheres, cylinders, and so on. Particles are idealized and treated as spheres in our study, while walls are represented by planes. MCRT relies on tracking a defined (i.e., large) number of rays that originate from random points under random angles, and the first intersection with another object is noted for each ray. The fraction of rays that are leaving the emitting object and intersecting with the absorbing object is then the view factor. The necessary number of rays and the effect of this number on the view factor distributions need to be understood to make precise predictions. The interested reader is referred to our section “Target” for detailed information about this computational detail.

3. Dataset creation and marker selection

Our preceding contribution (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) showed that view factors and their predictions are significantly affected by the particle volume fraction of the considered system. This applies to particle–particle as well as to particle–wall interactions. Therefore, we create datasets based on dense, moderately dense, and dilute particle beds with a particle volume fraction $\varphi_{p,sys}$ of 0.55, 0.40, and 0.20, respectively. Furthermore, the influence of the particle size distribution on the view factor prediction is investigated. A distinction is made between bi- and polydisperse datasets. In terms of the view factor distribution, three scenarios are important: (i) equal number fraction of smaller and bigger particles, (ii) more smaller particles, and (iii) more bigger particles. The division for bidisperse particle beds comes naturally. For polydisperse datasets, the separation is based on the arithmetic mean of the occurring particle diameters. In Table 1 an overview of all individually created datasets is given. The occurring particle radii r , the number-based species fraction n_s , and the total number of particles n_{tot} can be seen.

3.1. Particle bed generation

As mentioned in Section 2, all particle beds are created via DEM simulations, the parameters of these simulations are listed in Table 2. To increase the generalization of the derived models, the datasets also include different system and particle sizes. Changing the system and particle size also allows us to investigate whether dimensionless input markers are advantageous over dimensional input markers. The domain size of “Dense” systems is

$0.42 \times 0.42 \times 0.42$ (m), for “Moderately dense” and “Dilute” systems it is $8 \times 8 \times 8$ (m).

Dense systems are settled particle beds with high particle volume fraction. For these scenarios, particles were inserted into the system (i.e., a box with walls) and then settled under gravity until the kinetic energy reaches a minimum, which typically took about 20,000 time steps. For moderately dense and dilute systems particles are inserted without gravity and immediately frozen. It is important to note that overlap between particles is avoided for all our particle–particle datasets. When creating particle–wall particle beds, particle–wall overlaps are restricted. However, minimal particle–particle overlaps may occur. Otherwise, the insertion routine is the same.

The view factor calculation considers every inserted particle. This leads to a different number of target values for particle–particle and particle–wall interaction, e.g., the dataset “PolyDi – Dense 0” contains 173 particles (see Table 1) and therefore 173×172 particle–particle view factors. Particle–wall view factors are derived for top and bottom walls, leading to only 2×173 view factors. Therefore, we create 395 different particle beds for each particle–wall dataset based on random seeds to reach the same order of magnitude in terms of target values.

3.2. Targets

We refer to our preceding publication (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), where the general difference in the view factors distribution between particle–particle and particle–wall, as well as the difference between dense and moderately dense systems, is shown. In the present contribution, the view factors are similarly calculated using the Monte Carlo ray-tracing algorithm from Walker et al. (Walker et al., 2010). The ray density per unit area remains $1e6$ for moderately dense and dilute particle beds and $1e8$ for dense particle beds, the threshold view factor value is $5e-6$ as in (Forgber & Radl, 2018; Tausendschön & Radl, 2021). Thresholding is applied since very small view factors lead to negligibly small heat fluxes (Forgber & Radl, 2018; Tausendschön & Radl, 2021).

For regression tasks, the targeted view factors have a wide range from $O(10^{-1})$ to $O(10^{-6})$ or below (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021). This usually results in two difficulties when the Mean Squared Error (MSE) is used as cost function: (i) high view factor values have a significantly higher impact than small view factor values, and (ii) the MSE will be at the same level as the target at a small value

Table 1
Dataset overview.

Category	$\varphi_{p,sys}$ (-)	n_{tot} (-)	r (m)	n_s (-)
BiDi – Dense 0	0.55	166	0.045; 0.03	0.5; 0.5
BiDi – Dense 1	0.55	211	0.045; 0.03	0.3; 0.7
BiDi – Dense 2	0.55	136	0.045; 0.03	0.7; 0.3
BiDi – Moderately dense 0	0.40	551	0.5; 0.375	0.5; 0.5
BiDi – Moderately dense 1	0.40	658	0.5; 0.375	0.3; 0.7
BiDi – Moderately dense 2	0.40	474	0.5; 0.375	0.7; 0.3
BiDi – Dilute 0	0.20	276	0.5; 0.375	0.5; 0.5
BiDi – Dilute 1	0.20	329	0.5; 0.375	0.3; 0.7
BiDi – Dilute 2	0.20	237	0.5; 0.375	0.7; 0.3
PolyDi – Dense 0	0.55	173	0.045; 0.040; 0.035; 0.03	0.250; 0.250; 0.250; 0.250
PolyDi – Dense 1	0.55	139	0.045; 0.040; 0.035; 0.03	0.500; 0.250; 0.125; 0.125
PolyDi – Dense 2	0.55	224	0.045; 0.040; 0.035; 0.03	0.125; 0.125; 0.250; 0.500
PolyDi – Moderately dense 0	0.40	874	0.5; 0.4; 0.3; 0.2	0.250; 0.250; 0.250; 0.250
PolyDi – Moderately dense 1	0.40	590	0.5; 0.4; 0.3; 0.2	0.500; 0.250; 0.125; 0.125
PolyDi – Moderately dense 2	0.40	1423	0.5; 0.4; 0.3; 0.2	0.125; 0.125; 0.250; 0.500
PolyDi – Dilute 0	0.20	437	0.5; 0.4; 0.3; 0.2	0.250; 0.250; 0.250; 0.250
PolyDi – Dilute 1	0.20	297	0.5; 0.4; 0.3; 0.2	0.500; 0.250; 0.125; 0.125
PolyDi – Dilute 2	0.20	712	0.5; 0.4; 0.3; 0.2	0.125; 0.125; 0.250; 0.500

Table 2
General DEM parameters particle bed generation.

Property	Value
Particle density	2000 (kg/m ³)
Youngs modulus	5e6 (Pa)
Poisson ratio	0.45
Restitution coefficient	0.9
Friction coefficient	0.5
Characteristic velocity	1 (m/s)
Time step	1e-5 (s)

around $O(10^{-6})$ for given progress of the regression, which encourages overfitting. To tackle this issue, our marker analysis and selection is performed with the square root of the view factor as target value in addition. Taking the square root of the view factors ranging between 0 and 1 and then min-max normalizing results in a higher mean and a larger variance. Both effects can be beneficial for regression. In addition, the square root enables a simple back transformation.

3.3. Marker analysis

We have shown (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) that in mono-disperse systems a DNN can accurately predict view factors based on two input markers: (i) the inverse norm of particle center-center distance $1/|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j|$, and (ii) the number of particles $n_{pib,i-j}$ positioned between the emitting and absorbing particle within a hypothetical cylinder. To adapt to bi- and polydisperse systems and to avoid possible problems with the magnitude of the marker between particles of different sizes, the following possibilities to make the distance marker dimensionless are investigated: by the radius of the (i) absorbing particle, i.e., $r_j/|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j|$, the (ii) emitting particle, i.e., $r_i/|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j|$, and the (iii) geometric mean radius, i.e., $r_{eff}/|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j|$. Where the effective radius is defined by $r_{eff} = r_i r_j / (r_i + r_j)$. Dimensionless parameters allow application at any size scale, this could prove advantageous when combining data sets with different system sizes.

The second marker $n_{pib,i-j}$ is defined by the set of particles N (with center vector \mathbf{x}) that fulfill each of the following three equations (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021):

$$(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) > 0 \quad (3)$$

$$(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_j) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) < 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{|(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_i) \times (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i)|}{|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i|} \leq r_{search} \quad (5)$$

The second basic marker can be adapted on geometrical aspects in two ways: (i) change of the search radius r_{search} , or (ii) change of the hypothetical cylinder to a hypothetical truncated cone (see Fig. 2). For the search radius, the following possibilities are explored: (i) the radius of the emitting particle r_i , (ii) the radius of the absorbing particle r_j , (iii) the maximum particle radius of the emitting and the absorbing particle $r_{ij,max}$, and (iv) the maximum particle radius found in the whole particle bed r_{max} .

As can be seen in Fig. 2, the radii of the top and bottom surface of the truncated cone are defined by the emitting and absorbing particle radius. One has to note that this potential adjustment is computationally more expensive than the calculation for the hypothetical cylinder, since the search radius of the truncated cone then depends on the position of the particle on the cone axes. The search radius is then described by:

$$r_{search}(\mathbf{x}) = r_i - \frac{|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}|}{|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j|} (r_i - r_j) \quad (6)$$

where $|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}|$ denotes the distance of the intersection point \mathbf{x}_S to the center of the emitting particle \mathbf{x}_i . The intersection point is determined via an auxiliary plane that intersects with the cone axis:

$$\mathbf{x}_S = \mathbf{x} + \lambda (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) \quad (7)$$

where λ is defined by:

$$\lambda = \frac{\mathbf{x} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) - \mathbf{x}_i \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i)}{(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i)} \quad (8)$$

The third marker group, besides the distance and the shadowing particle group, is related to the particle size. First, it is obvious that particle size could be an important marker; second, empirical relationships describing heat transfer in polydisperse particle beds usually contain information about particle size (Gupta et al., 2002; Peng et al., 2020). Therefore, we investigate the direct addition of the absorbing radius r_j , as well as the addition of the particle size

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the determination of the number between the emitting particle in red and the absorbing particle in green, on the left for a basic hypothetical cylinder and in the middle panel for an adjusted hypothetical truncated cone. The right panel shows the determination of particles within a sphere around the emitting particle (the green absorbing particle is here irrelevant). The detected particles in the respective hypothetical region are shown in blue, while the particles outside are grey with dashed outlines. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

ratio r_j/r_i . An overview of all particle–particle interaction markers and their definitions is given in Table A1 in Appendix A.

Beside the discussed interaction markers, the particle volume fraction is investigated as a non-interaction input marker in the following forms: (i) the system particle volume fraction $\varphi_{p,sys}$, (ii) the volume fraction of the smallest particle species $\varphi_{p,r_{min}}$, and (iii) of the biggest particle species $\varphi_{p,r_{max}}$, (iv) the local particle volume fraction within a hypothetical sphere $\varphi_{p,S}$ (see Fig. 2), (v) the local particle volume fraction in a cubic mesh grid $\varphi_{p,C}$, and (vi) the number of particles in a hypothetical sphere around the emitting particle n_{piS} (see Fig. 2). On the right side of Fig. 2 the hypothetical sphere used for determining $\varphi_{p,S}$ and n_{piS} is schematically illustrated. For n_{piS} a particle with center vector \mathbf{x} is counted to be within the hypothetical sphere if the following equation is fulfilled:

$$|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_i| < r_{search} \quad (9)$$

For $\varphi_{p,S}$ every particle inside the sphere, even if only partially, i.e. $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_i| - r < r_{search}$, is considered. S_i designates the set of these particles within the sphere of particle i . Then, the analytically exact volume within the sphere $V_{seg,p,i}$ of particles that are an element of S_i is calculated. The search radius of the hypothetical sphere is defined as two times the maximum particle radius for both markers. The local particle volume fraction in a cubic mesh grid is explored as the connection to CFD-DEM simulations, where this marker is available without additional computational cost. The cubic mesh has an edge length of four times the maximum particle radius, which is a typical size for CFD-DEM simulations. The volume fraction within the cube is calculated via Monte Carlo integration, the interested reader is referred to Appendix B for details of the integration. Since these markers depend only on the particle itself and its environment, and not on any particular interaction partner, they can be applied to particle–particle and particle–wall view factors. Table A2 in Appendix A summarizes these markers and their definitions.

In our previous study (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) the markers for particle–wall view factors are based on the same calculation principles as particle–particle markers. The basic distance marker is the inverse norm of the normal distance vector $1/|\mathbf{n}_{wall-i}|$. As described for particle–particle interaction, the possibility to non-dimensionalize the distance with the particle radius is investigated for particle–wall interaction too. This yields the marker $r_i/|\mathbf{n}_{wall-i}|$.

To calculate the number of particles between the emitting wall and the absorbing particle $n_{pib,wall-i}$, the hypothetical cylinder, in Eqs. (3)–(5), is spanned from the center of the wall to the respective particle (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021). As a possible adaptation for bi- and polydisperse particle beds, the search radius is changed to (i) the actual radius of the interacting particle or (ii) the maximum particle radius in the particle bed.

Similar to for particle–particle interaction, particle size-related markers are tested for particle–wall interaction in form of the direct addition of the particle radius r_i , and as ratio of the particle and wall surface A_i/A_{wall} . Table A3 gives an overview of all interaction-based particle–wall markers and their definitions in Appendix A.

3.4. Marker selection

To describe the quality of correlation between the marker and the target, two different parameters are used. The Pearson correlation coefficient $\rho_{X,Y}$ is the first parameter and describes the linear relation between two populations X and Y by:

$$\rho_{X,Y} = \frac{Cov(X, Y)}{\sigma_X \sigma_Y} \quad (10)$$

σ_X and σ_Y are the standard deviations of the respective population. To assess how well the relation between the marker and the view factor can be described with a monotonic function, the Spearman rank correlation coefficient r_S is chosen as the second parameter and is defined via:

$$r_S = \frac{Cov(r_{g,X}, r_{g,Y})}{\sigma_{r_{g,X}} \sigma_{r_{g,Y}}} \quad (11)$$

Here $r_{g,X}$ and $r_{g,Y}$ are the ranks of a quantity, where the smallest value has rank 1. $\sigma_{r_{g,X}}$ and $\sigma_{r_{g,Y}}$ are the standard deviations of the respective ranking.

To quantify the predictive power connected to different choices for the markers, a broad dataset based on three different levels is used. The first level is narrowly specified to test the correlation for a specific particle volume fraction. The second level tests (i) the global particle volume fraction as a marker, (ii) the marker ability to deal with different system sizes, and (iii) the correlation across all particle volume fractions differentiated between bi- and polydisperse particle beds. The third level dataset then combines bi-

Table 3
Dataset structure for marker analysis.

Third level dataset	Second level dataset	First level dataset	Category	$\varphi_{p,sys} (-)$	
Total (includes $\varphi_{p,sys}$ as marker)	Bidisperse – Total (includes $\varphi_{p,sys}$ as marker)	Bidisperse – Dense	BiDi – Dense 0	0.55	
			BiDi – Dense 1	0.55	
			BiDi – Dense 2	0.55	
		Bidisperse – Moderately dense	BiDi – Moderately dense 0	0.40	
			BiDi – Moderately dense 1	0.40	
			BiDi – Moderately dense 2	0.40	
			Bidisperse – Dilute	0.20	
		Polydisperse – Total (includes $\varphi_{p,sys}$ as marker)	Polydisperse – Dense	BiDi – Dilute 0	0.20
				BiDi – Dilute 1	0.20
				BiDi – Dilute 2	0.20
	Polydisperse – Moderately dense		PolyDi – Dense 0	0.55	
			PolyDi – Dense 1	0.55	
			PolyDi – Dense 2	0.55	
	Polydisperse – Dilute	Polydisperse – Moderately dense	PolyDi – Moderately dense 0	0.40	
			PolyDi – Moderately dense 1	0.40	
			PolyDi – Moderately dense 2	0.40	
		Polydisperse – Dilute	PolyDi – Dilute 0	0.20	
			PolyDi – Dilute 1	0.20	
			PolyDi – Dilute 2	0.20	

and polydisperse particle sub-datasets. In Table 3 the detailed dataset structure is shown.

3.4.1. Particle–particle marker selection

In Table 4 all determined correlation coefficients for particle–particle view factors on the third level dataset can be seen. One has to note that transforming the target by taking the square root does not influence the Spearman coefficient.

In the distance group, the dimensionless markers have a significantly higher correlation than the dimensioned distance marker. $r_j/|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|$ and $r_{eff}/|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|$ yield higher correlations than $r_i/|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|$ for the normal and the transformed target. Finally, $r_j/|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|$ is selected since the calculation of r_{eff} needs additional effort and does not result in a better correlation.

The direct addition of the emitting particle radius resulted in a higher correlation to the target, compared to adding the size ratio. Both markers only yield low correlations compared to the distance markers. However, preliminary tests have shown that the size information is important. Therefore, we select the dimensionless quantity r_j/r_i over the dimensioned as the second marker. The transformation of the target increased both correlations at a very low level.

Table 4
Calculated correlation coefficients for particle–particle interactions on the third level (total) dataset.

Marker	Pearson coeff.	Spearman coeff.	Pearson coeff. for $\sqrt{e_{i-j}}$
$1/ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} $	0.35	0.59	0.34
$r_j/ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} $	0.73	0.64	0.86
$r_{eff}/ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} $	0.73	0.64	0.86
$r_i/ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} $	0.62	0.59	0.77
r_j	0.05	0.21	0.11
r_j/r_i	0.05	0.05	0.06
$n_{pib,i-j,r_i}$	-0.12	-0.51	-0.22
$n_{pib,i-j,r_j}$	-0.15	-0.43	-0.26
$n_{pib,i-j,r_{max}}$	-0.21	-0.65	-0.38
$n_{pib,i-j,r_{i,max}}$	-0.17	-0.49	-0.30
$n_{pib,i-j,TC}$	-0.06	-0.10	-0.10
n_{piS}	-0.03	-0.22	-0.19
$\varphi_{p,sys}$	0.02	-0.29	-0.07
$\varphi_{p,r_{min}}$	0.04	-0.04	0.03
$\varphi_{p,r_{max}}$	0.05	-0.07	0.02
$\varphi_{p,S}$	-0.01	-0.27	-0.09
$\varphi_{p,C}$	0.01	-0.23	-0.08

Among the several ways to determine the number of particles between the emitting and the absorbing particle, $n_{pib,i-j,r_{max}}$ which is based on the maximum particle radius, achieved the highest coefficient in all three categories and is therefore selected as the third marker. From the usage of the truncated cone, the lowest coefficients were obtained.

From the non-interaction markers, we select $\varphi_{p,sys}$, i.e., the global particle volume fraction of the system. It has the highest nonlinear correlation to the target. The additional computational effort to determine n_{piS} , $\varphi_{p,S}$, or $\varphi_{p,C}$ combined with the low correlations leads to discarding these markers. Although, the use of the local particle volume fraction $\varphi_{p,C}$ could be considered when conducting CFD-DEM simulations, since this parameter is then usually available without additional computational costs. As a first attempt, we investigate the discussed ML-based models with three input markers, the input vector ψ is then defined as:

$$\psi_{PP,3M} = \left(\frac{r_j}{|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|}, n_{pib,i-j,r_{max}}, \frac{r_j}{r_i} \right) \tag{12}$$

When training the models on datasets with different particle volume fractions, we explore the addition of the non-interaction marker $\varphi_{p,sys}$ as a fourth input marker in a second attempt. This leads to the following input vector:

$$\psi_{PP,4M} = \left(\frac{r_j}{|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|}, n_{pib,i-j,r_{max}}, \frac{r_j}{r_i}, \varphi_{p,sys} \right) \tag{13}$$

The transformation of the target increased most correlations coefficients compared to the normal non-transformed target. Therefore, the described ML-based models are also tested with datasets based on transformed targets.

3.4.2. Particle–wall marker selection

In Table 5, all determined correlation coefficients for particle–wall view factors on the third level dataset can be seen. From the particle–wall distance markers, the ratio of the particle radius and the normal distance to the wall $r_i/|\mathbf{n}_{wall-i}|$ has the highest correlations to the target and is therefore selected as the first marker. In the second category, $n_{pib,wall-i,r_{max}}$ and $n_{pib,wall-i,r_i}$ achieve nearly similar correlations. However, $n_{pib,wall-i,r_{max}}$ is chosen as the second marker because the sum of the correlations is slightly higher and the particle–wall ML models then rely on the same principles as the particle–particle models. Similar to

Table 5
Calculated correlation coefficients for particle–wall interactions on the third level (total) dataset.

Marker	Pearson coeff.	Spearman coeff.	Pearson coeff. for $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wall-i}}$
$1/ \mathbf{n}_{wall-i} $	0.70	0.57	0.59
$r_i/ \mathbf{n}_{wall-i} $	0.85	0.77	0.91
r_i	-0.10	0.21	0.03
A_i/A_{wall}	0.32	0.20	0.26
$n_{pib,wall-i,r_i}$	-0.28	-0.47	-0.40
$n_{pib,wall-i,r_{max}}$	-0.27	-0.50	-0.40
n_{piS}	-0.14	-0.33	-0.23
$\varphi_{p,sys}$	0.12	-0.25	-0.02
$\varphi_{p,r_{min}}$	0.08	-0.04	0.04
$\varphi_{p,r_{max}}$	0.14	-0.14	0.06
$\varphi_{p,S}$	-0.04	-0.24	-0.12
$\varphi_{p,C}$	0.03	-0.23	-0.08

particle–particle results we dismiss the direct addition of the particle radius r_i , since it is dimensioned and the determined coefficients are lower than the coefficients of A_i/A_{wall} . The third input marker is then A_i/A_{wall} . In the non-interaction group, one can draw the same conclusions as in the particle–particle case and select $\varphi_{p,sys}$ as the fourth input marker.

In the fourth category, n_{piS} has the highest correlation coefficients, at an overall mediocre level. The additional computational and the mediocre level cost lead to dismissing this marker. The correlation coefficients of $\varphi_{p,sys}$ are close to ones of n_{piS} . However, the marker $\varphi_{p,sys}$ is available without notable computational effort. Thus, $\varphi_{p,sys}$ is selected as the fourth input marker. In principle, one finds the same conclusions as for particle–particle markers. Thus, for the final setup, we also first investigate the discussed ML-based models with three input markers, the particle–wall input vector ψ_{PW} is then defined as follows:

$$\psi_{PW,3M} = \left(\frac{r_i}{|\mathbf{n}_{wall-i}|}, \frac{A_i}{A_{wall}}, n_{pib,wall-i,r_{max}} \right) \tag{14}$$

Similar to particle–particle models, the addition of the fourth marker is investigated when the training on datasets with different particle volume fractions. The particle–wall input vector ψ_{PW} with four input markers is then defined by:

$$\psi_{PW,4M} = \left(\frac{r_i}{|\mathbf{n}_{wall-i}|}, \frac{A_i}{A_{wall}}, n_{pib,wall-i,r_{max}}, \varphi_{p,sys} \right) \tag{15}$$

In the case of particle–wall interactions, correlations with the square root of the target show a more differentiated picture than for particle–particle interactions. The coefficients for A_i/A_{wall} and $\varphi_{p,sys}$ decrease, while they increase for $n_{pib,wall-i,r_{max}}$ and $r_i/|\mathbf{n}_{wall-i}|$. Nonetheless, we explore the possibility of transforming the target by taking the square root for particle–wall view factors.

4. Machine Learning-based models

In order to make a meaningful comparison, all Machine Learning-based models are trained, validated, and tested with the same datasets and are based on the same markers. In our previous study (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) we examined the ratio of training, validation, and testing data to the total dataset for a DNN and found that ratios of 0.80, 0.10, and 0.10, respectively, are sufficient. These values are adopted for all models in our present contribution. A key task for all used ML-based models is the model parameter optimization. Based on the randomized search approach (Bergstra & Bengio, 2012), the best possible generalization of each model is searched. The randomized search optimization and the preparation of the raw data were performed using the Scikit-learn®

environment. Training and selection of the final models are based on stratified k-fold cross-validation (Raschka, 2018). The number of k-fold is equal to five over all performed searches. To ensure a computationally feasible hyperparameter search the number of random parameter combinations is limited to ten.

The Section “Targets” already described the thresholding of small view factors. Thresholding is applied to the training data and to the prediction of the models. Neural networks typically require feature scaling (or normalization) of the input markers (Heaton, 2015; Ioffe & Szegedy, 2015). Feature scaling is not required for decision tree-based algorithms, and thus for Random Forest or gradient boosting regressors, since they are not distance-based (Breiman, 2001; Chen & Guestrin, 2016). However, the use of normalized data does not affect their outcome. The normalization of an input marker ψ_i in our present study follows:

$$\tilde{\psi}_i = (\psi_i - \psi_{min,i}) / (\psi_{max,i} - \psi_{min,i}) \tag{16}$$

where $\tilde{\psi}_i$ is then the normalized input marker. The targeted view factors (here designated as z) are also normalized based on min- and max-values:

$$\tilde{z} = \frac{z - \epsilon_{min}}{\epsilon_{max} - \epsilon_{min}} \tag{17}$$

\tilde{z} denotes the normalized target. To obtain the denormalized prediction, Eq. (17) is rearranged for z . For the normalization of the input markers and the target the respective min- and max-values are searched in the training data and then used to normalize (and denormalize) the validation and the testing data to avoid data leakage (Kaufman et al., 2011). When using a pre-trained model for prediction, the input data is normalized with min- and max-values based on the new input data. Similar to our previous study (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) the prediction is then denormalized by using the analytical maximum view factor as ϵ_{max} , and 0 as ϵ_{min} .

Another key task for a learning algorithm is the choice of the cost function (or the criterion). In our previous study (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), the Mean Squared Error (MSE) was chosen for the presented DNNs. In this paper, we adopt the MSE to all presented ML algorithms. The MSE is calculated as follows:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (z_{pred} - z_{target})^2 \tag{18}$$

It should be noted that the Huber loss function was tested for DNNs as an alternative to the MSE. However, no significant improvements could be achieved. The MSE is significantly more affected by large view factors, so the coefficient of determination

(R^2) is also used to describe the correlation between prediction and target:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (z_{target} - z_{pred})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (z_{target} - \bar{z}_{target})^2} \quad (19)$$

\bar{z}_{target} is the arithmetic mean value of all considered targets. In our previous study (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) the coefficient of determination (R_{spread}^2) for particle–particle (or particle–wall normal) distances within a certain range (defined by the lower boundary x_U and the upper boundary x_O) was introduced as:

$$R_{spread}^2(x_U, x_O) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (z_{target}(|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|) - z_{pred}(|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|))^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (z_{target}(|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|) - \bar{z}_{target}(|\mathbf{x}_{i-j}|))^2} \quad (20)$$

for $x_U \leq |\mathbf{x}_{i-j}| \leq x_O$

Based on the arithmetic mean particle diameter \bar{d}_p , x_U equals half of the domain size minus $1.5 \bar{d}_p$, while x_O is half of the domain size plus $1.5 \bar{d}_p$.

4.1. Deep Neural Networks

Deep Neural Networks quickly became a standard regression tool for many applications. Therefore, we only briefly summarize our implementation. The outcome \tilde{z} of a simple single non-linear neuron is defined as:

$$\tilde{z} = h(\mathbf{w}^T \tilde{\psi} + w_0) \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the weight vector, w_0 is the bias, and h is the applied activation function. The creation and the training of all DNNs was performed within the Keras® framework in Python®.

The number of nodes in the input layer equals the number of selected markers. The desired output, a single target view factor, defines the output layer and the number of nodes. In contrast to our previous work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), DNNs with more than one hidden layer, namely two or three hidden layers, are explored. Typically for regressions tasks, each hidden layer is followed by a Rectifying Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function (Goodfellow et al., 2016), while no activation function is applied to the output layer (Heaton, 2015). Randomized search is performed separately for one, two, or three hidden layer networks (Radosavovic et al., 2020; Smith, 2018). Two regularization options are examined: (i) early stopping with a patience parameter of zero (Prechelt, 2012), and (ii) dropout (Srivastava et al., 2014) considering different dropout rates. Dropout is added in form of an additional layer after a hidden layer. DNNs without regularization are also tested, here the dropout rate is set to zero. Additional to the standard Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimizer, the following advanced optimizers are tested: Adam (Kingma & Ba, 2015), Adagrad (Duchi et al., 2011), and RMSprop (Tieleman & Hinton, 2012). It should be noted that apart from changing the learning rate, no other adjustments are made to the optimizers.

Mini-batch gradient descent is used as a variation of the gradient descent algorithm (Li et al., 2014) to increase the overall efficiency of the training process. The mini-batch size is equal to the summed-up number of particles in each dataset, e.g. the first level dataset “Polydisperse – Dense” has a batch size of 536 (=

173 + 139+224 see Table 1). Consequently, the mini-batch size is not part of the randomized search approach.

Table 6 summarizes the searched hyperparameters and shows the found optima for particle–particle and particle–wall interactions. All searches were performed with the three marker-neural networks (for P–P and P–W see Eq. (12) and Eq. (14) respectively). Four marker-DNNs use the same hyperparameters derived for their three-marker counterpart. For the selected possibilities of the number of hidden nodes n_{hidd} , we follow our previous publication (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021). In the case of two or three hidden layer networks, the found number of hidden nodes is the same in every layer.

4.2. Random Forest Regressor

The Random Forest Regressor (RFR) is also an ensemble model. It is based on bagging applied to decision trees (Breiman, 2001; Liaw & Wiener, 2002). A Random Forest constructs several decision trees (see Fig. 3) during training and combines the trees’ predictions by taking the average of all trees. RFRs are powerful and fast. However, unlike DNNs, they cannot extrapolate, i.e., the predicted values are always within the training set values (Hengl et al., 2018). Therefore, careful data set generation is essential.

The implementation of the RFR is performed using the Scikit-learn® environment. The varied hyperparameters of the RFR are: (i) number of trees in the Random Forest $n_{tree,rf}$, (ii) the maximum number of levels $n_{max,depth}$ in these trees, (iii) the minimum number of samples $n_{min,split}$ required to split a node, (iv) the minimum number of samples required at each leaf node $n_{min,samples}$, and (v) whether the samples are drawn with or without bootstrapping. In Table 7 all searched parameter options and the found optimum for particle–particle as well as particle–wall view factors are shown.

4.3. Extreme Gradient Boosting Regressor

Gradient boosting of decision trees is also an ensemble method. Unlike RFR, the boosting algorithm builds new learners (in this case, decision trees) sequentially rather than in parallel (see Fig. 4). In this way, the subsequent predictor can learn from the previous predictor by weighting the observations, i.e., increasing the weight of incorrect predictions and high errors. The weights are then optimized based on the gradients, which requires a differentiable loss function - the second significant difference to RFRs. Therefore, the predictions of the final ensemble model are the weighted sum of the previous trees’ predictions.

We use the implementation of Chen and Guestrin (Chen & Guestrin, 2016), called XGBoost®, which stands for Extreme Gradient Boosting. Unlike the standard gradient boosting described above, XGBoost® uses second-order gradients, advanced regularization, and is highly optimized. In the randomized search, the following hyperparameters are optimized: (i) the learning rate, (ii) the usage of a tree or linear booster, (iii) the number of gradient-boosted trees $n_{est,xgb}$, (iv) the maximum depth of a tree $n_{tree,xgb}$, and (v) the minimum sum of instance weight (hessian) needed in a child $n_{min,child}$. Table 8 summarizes all hyperparameters and the optima found.

4.4. Deep Neural Network ensembles

The main idea of Deep Neural Network stacking ensembles is to combine predictions of single Deep Neural Networks to achieve better predictions than with a single network. There are two main structures for such ensembles: integrated and separated. Unlike the separated ones, the integrated stacking ensemble can be treated as a single large model (Ganaie et al., 2021; Wolpert, 1992). Thus, we

Table 6
Summary of hyperparameters for DNNs based on the third level dataset.

Hyperparameters	Searched options	Found P–P optimum	Found P–W optimum
n_{hid}	25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200	100	125
Init weights	“he uniform” (He et al., 2015), “he normal” (He et al., 2015), “zeros”	“he uniform”	“he uniform”
Optimizer	Adam (Kingma & Ba, 2015), SGD, Adagrad (Duchi et al., 2011), RMSprop (Tieleman & Hinton, 2012)	Adam	RMSprop
Learning rate	1e-3, 8e-4, 5e-4, 3e-4, 1e-4	0.001	0.0005
Hidden layers	1, 2, 3	1	3
Batch normalization	On/Off	Off	Off
Epochs	10, 25, 50, 100, 200	200	200
Dropout rate	0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1	0	0.02
Early stopping	On/Off	Off	Off

Fig. 3. Random Forest Regressor principle.

Table 7
Summary of hyperparameters for RFRs based on the third level dataset.

Hyperparameters	Searched options	Found P–P optimum	Found P–W optimum
$n_{tree,rf}$	100, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000	200	600
$n_{max,depth}$	None, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100	30	20
$n_{min,split}$	2, 5, 10	10	10
$n_{min,samples}$	1, 2, 4	1	2
Bootstrapping	On/Off	On	On

focus on the integrated stacking ensemble, since the desired application is the usage in a DEM simulation, where the loading and evaluation of several NNs, as needed for the separated ensembles, is computationally too demanding.

In Fig. 5 the principle of the used ensembles can be seen. DNNs, as described in the previous section, represent level 0 models. The output of the level 0 models is then provided directly to the meta-learner. The new level 1 model, also called meta learner, has a hidden layer that interprets this input. The output layer of the meta learner then makes its probabilistic prediction. The training of such ensembles takes place in two stages: in the first step each DNN in level 0 is trained, in the second step the level 1 model is trained with holdout data, where the sub-model weights are not updated, but only the hidden and the output layer are trained. Consequently,

the datasets must be restructured by changing the train, validation and testing splits. For the training of the single networks 70%, for the validation 10%, and for the training of the meta-network 10% of each particle bed of the whole dataset are used. The remaining 10% are then used to test the neural network ensemble.

Level 0 models are based on first level datasets, resulting in six sub-models that are then combined. Each DNN of level 0 has the same structure and hyperparameters, derived from the optimization of the respective normal DNNs (see Table 6). Only for particle–wall DNNs in level 0, the number of hidden layers is set to 1, instead of 3 as stated in Table 9, to maintain a necessary simplicity. Overall, the number of epochs is limited to 20 in level 0, and dropout is applied with a rate of 0.02 to keep the computational training effort feasible (see Appendix E).

Fig. 4. Gradient boosting principle.

Table 8
Summary of hyperparameters for XGBRs based on the third level dataset.

Hyperparameters	Searched options	Found P–P optimum	Found P–W optimum
Learning rate	0.5, 0.1, 0.01, 0.005, 0.001	0.1	0.5
Booster	Tree/Linear	Tree	Tree
$n_{est.xgb}$	50, 100, 200, 400, 600	100	100
$n_{tree.xgb}$	3, 6, 12, 24	3	12
$n_{min.child}$	1, 5, 10, 15, 20	5	20

Fig. 5. Principle of stacked DNN ensemble.

Table 9
Metrics of all three marker models for particle–particle view factors.

Model	Target	MSE_{Test}	R^2_{test}	$R^2_{spread, test}$
DNN	Normal	6.965e-7	0.9752	-0.0060
	Transformed	6.578e-7	0.9766	0.1508
RFR	Normal	6.342e-7	0.9774	-0.2393
	Transformed	6.671e-7	0.9763	0.1059
XGB	Normal	5.877e-6	0.7909	-0.4497
	Transformed	6.160e-6	0.7808	0.0123
eDNN	Normal	7.299e-7	0.9775	-0.5701
	Transformed	6.732e-7	0.9792	-0.0016

The hyperparameters of the meta learners are also taken from the randomized search optimization of the basic DNNs (see Table 6). The structure is given by the type of ensemble, as mentioned above, also see Fig. 5.

5. Results

In this section the results are shown separately for particle–particle and particle–wall view factors. A further subdivision is made between the available three- and four-marker models and between models that were trained and tested with a normal or transformed target. All shown predictions and quality metrics are based on the total test dataset for particle–particle and particle–wall interaction (equal to the third level in Table 3). It should be noted that the test datasets of the ensemble of DNNs (hereafter referred to as eDNNs) are slightly different from the test datasets of the other models, as described in Section 4.4. However, this does not affect the comparability in terms of generalization behavior, since both datasets are composed of the same particle beds and structured in the same way.

5.1. Particle–particle dataset

5.1.1. Three marker models

Fig. 6 shows all ML-based model results using three markers and trained with the normal target. Table 9 summarizes all prediction metrics, including the outcome of models trained with the transformed target. The respective predictions of the models trained with transformed data can be seen in Appendix C1. In our prior work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), the values for MSE , R^2 , and R^2_{spread} for a monodisperse system were around $3e-7$, 0.993, and 0.701, respectively. In terms of the MSE , the same order of magnitude is reached for bi- and polydisperse data using a DNN, RFR, or an eDNN. However, the overall R^2 values are significantly lower, and no meaningful correlation could be achieved for R^2_{spread} . The overall prediction quality of the XGB regressor is significantly worse.

When training with transformed targets, no significant improvement can be achieved in terms of the MSE or R^2 for all models (see Table 9). R^2_{spread} values increased, however still no meaningful correlation is yielded. Regardless of whether training the three marker-networks with normal or transformed targets, the results of R^2_{spread} are not satisfactory.

5.1.2. Four marker models

The addition of the fourth marker slightly improved the MSE and significantly improved R^2 overall, except for the eDNN, which hardly benefits from the fourth marker. Again, the XGB regressor performs poorly (see Table 10 and Fig. 7). The RFR performs superior in terms of MSE and R^2 . The RFR also achieves an R^2_{spread} value at a sufficient scale, according to our previous study (Tausendschön &

Radl, 2021). The DNN-metrics are close to the RFR-metrics. Appendix C2 shows the respective predictions of the models trained with transformed data.

Overall, the addition of the fourth marker significantly improved the prediction quality. It is therefore recommended to use four-marker models, especially since the additional computational effort is very small (see Appendix E for a discussion of computational costs).

5.2. Particle–wall dataset

5.2.1. Three marker models

The predictions of three marker models for particle–wall view factors can be seen in Fig. 8. The quality metrics, including data from models trained with transformed targets, are listed in Table 11. MSE , R^2 , and R^2_{spread} for particle–wall view factors in a monodisperse system (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) were around $6e-8$, 0.9506, and 0.6003, respectively. The overall MSE s obtained are an order of magnitude higher as in our previous study (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021). As evident from the shown R^2 values, this does not necessarily indicate worse prediction, only different magnitudes in the target values. The mean target value in the training data set here is $1.671e-3$, while in our previous work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), it was $7.678e-4$. The obtained R^2 and R^2_{spread} values are equal or higher than in our previous work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021).

Compared to the other models, the prediction of XGBoost® models is significantly better for particle–wall than for particle–particle view factors. This is understandable since the particle–wall distribution of view factors is significantly different from the particle–particle distribution when comparing, for example, Fig. 6 with Fig. 8. Furthermore, the prediction of the RFRs is also better for particle–wall, which is also based on decision trees. Again, no improvement could be achieved by using ensembles rather than a single DNN. The RFR is superior, as can be seen in Fig. 8 and Table 11. It yields very high R^2 and R^2_{spread} values and the smallest MSE .

Besides the RFR, where only a minimal improvement was realized, the training with transformed targets did not enhance the prediction quality (for the respective predictions of the models trained with transformed data, see Appendix D1).

5.2.2. Four marker models

Adding the particle volume fraction of the system as the fourth marker has a lower impact for particle–wall than for particle–particle view factors. For DNNs, a small improvement can be observed for all three metrics, see Table 12. The results of the RFRs, especially R^2_{spread} values, are also better using four than three markers. A significant increase in the prediction quality is realized for XGBoost®-regressors. The conclusion for eDNNs is different for training with normal or transformed targets. The former slightly improved the model results, while the latter significantly boosted the prediction abilities. Similar to Fig. 9, the prediction plots of models trained with transformed targets can be found in Appendix D2.

Overall using four-marker models results in better predictions than three-marker models. This is true for particle–particle as well particle–wall view factors. In contrast to particle–particle interaction, the RFR is superior to the DNN for particle–wall interaction.

Training with transformed target values sometimes significantly improves the results of individual models. However, such a transformation does not represent a general improvement of the best models and is therefore not recommended.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle–particle dataset of three marker models.

Table 10
Metrics of all four marker models for particle–particle view factors.

Model	Target	MSE_{Test}	R^2_{test}	$R^2_{Spread.test}$
DNN	Normal	4.646e-7	0.9835	0.5197
	Transformed	5.250e-7	0.9813	0.5251
RFR	Normal	3.609e-7	0.9872	0.5884
	Transformed	3.713e-7	0.9868	0.5830
XGB	Normal	5.477e-6	0.8052	0.3915
	Transformed	5.849e-6	0.7919	0.5354
eDNN	Normal	6.947e-7	0.9786	-0.2836
	Transformed	6.785e-7	0.9791	0.0603

A quantitative answer why certain models perform better than others is difficult in machine learning. As shown, DNNs and RFRs are quite equivalent in terms of accuracy. This calls for consideration of why the other two model types are performing worse. For the eDNN, one reason might be that size of the level 1 (meta) training dataset is too small compared to the size of the level 0 dataset. There may be not enough training data to overcome the trained level 0 specialization, which data origins in narrowly

specified particle systems, to reach a model with a higher generalization in the end. The second reason might be that the hyper-parameters or the structure of the level 0 networks are not individually tuned. Such individual optimization might lead to higher total accuracy. However, a significant change in the training and testing data, which might solve the first issue, significantly reduces the ability to compare the outcome of the eDNN to the other presented models. Individual optimization of each level 0 model addresses the second issue but is very time-consuming, a higher level 1 accuracy is not guaranteed, and the first issue remains. Additionally, the fact that the eDNN will be any case slower than the DNN strengthens the recommendation to use the DNN or the RFR.

XGB models are often compared to RFR models since both are ensemble methods containing decision trees. A significant difference in the performance of the RFR is then usually explained by noisy data where boosting performs worse (Schapire & Freund, 2013) or that XGB models are harder to tune. A quantitative evaluation of the latter argument is not reasonably possible. The Monte Carlo-based view factor calculation is random to a certain extent and fluctuating, especially for smaller view factors. Qualitatively

Fig. 7. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle–particle dataset of four marker models.

this can be seen in Figs. 6–9. Therefore, the present data can be described as noisy and is beneficial to the RFR.

For concluding considerations of how the accuracy (or inaccuracy) of the view factor prediction affects the prediction of the transferred heat flux by thermal radiation and further the total heat flux, there exists – unfortunately - no experimental data available for comparison. In our previous work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021) it was shown that the DNN-based heat flux prediction is significantly influenced by other heat flux mechanism, such as heat conduction. The same applies to the other investigated models. Heat conduction models used in DEM simulations typically demand significant effort calibrating their simulation parameters, as shown in our previous work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021). However, this leads back to the original problem of missing experimental data for such a calibration in polydisperse systems. Therefore, the focus is on the accuracy of the view factor prediction, where we can conclude that the same level of accuracy for polydisperse systems is achieved as for monodisperse systems in our previous work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021).

6. Conclusion

Previously, we have shown the advantages of a DNN-based view factor calculation (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), which was limited to monodisperse systems. Therefore, the use of DNNs was adapted for bi- and polydisperse systems in our present contribution. The reason was that only one recent study examined particle–particle and particle–wall view factors for polydisperse particle beds (Malinouski & Rabinovich, 2017).

Consequently, a systematic analysis was performed to calculate view factors for bi- and polydisperse particle beds, including walls. Particle beds ranging from dilute to densely packed beds were considered in varying system dimensions. In addition, different scenarios were considered with respect to the fraction of each particle species.

Also, the application of other Machine Learning-based models was studied in our present work. Many contributions in recent literature (Desu et al., 2019; Kang et al., 2019; Tausendschön & Radl, 2021; Wu et al., 2020; Yarahmadi et al., 2020) simply rely on DNNs

Fig. 8. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle-wall dataset of three marker models.

Table 11

Metrics of all three marker models for particle-wall view factors.

Model	Target	MSE_{Test}	R^2_{test}	$R^2_{spread,test}$
DNN	Normal	7.635e-7	0.9653	0.3954
	Transformed	9.358e-7	0.9575	0.4064
RFR	Normal	3.701e-7	0.9832	0.8637
	Transformed	3.721e-7	0.9831	0.8821
XGB	Normal	9.300e-7	0.9578	0.5300
	Transformed	9.497e-7	0.9569	0.5163
eDNN	Normal	1.047e-6	0.9525	-0.1105
	Transformed	1.080e-6	0.9510	0.2864

for regression, overlooking other models that could be useful. Possibilities such as ensembles of DNNs, regressors based on Random Forests, or Extreme Gradient Boosting were therefore explored in detail by us.

In the course of our present research, the introduction of dimensionless input markers was investigated to deal with a

Table 12

Metrics of all four marker models for particle-wall view factors.

Model	Target	MSE_{Test}	R^2_{test}	$R^2_{spread,test}$
DNN	Normal	5.009e-7	0.9773	0.6915
	Transformed	6.420e-7	0.9708	0.7186
RFR	Normal	2.308e-7	0.9895	0.9618
	Transformed	2.294e-7	0.9896	0.9601
XGB	Normal	6.507e-7	0.9705	0.8618
	Transformed	6.647e-7	0.9698	0.8593
eDNN	Normal	9.281e-7	0.9579	0.0870
	Transformed	9.161e-7	0.9584	0.6218

multidimensional dataset. A clear advantage of dimensionless input markers over dimensioned ones can be reported. The marker analysis, as well as the subsequent results, revealed that the addition of a third marker containing particle size information enables the transition from monodisperse to bi- and polydisperse systems. However, the use of four markers is recommended, as can be seen

Fig. 9. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle–wall dataset of four marker models.

from our present results that indicate a clear gain in predictive power.

Ensembles of DNNs and XGBoost-regressor are overall worse than single DNNs or Random Forest regressors. While for particle–particle interaction DNNs and RFRs are pretty much on a par, the RFR is superior for particle–wall interactions. Nonetheless, also the presented particle–wall DNNs offer precise predictions. Besides the prediction quality, Random Forest Regressors provide the additional advantage of faster training and the possible benefit that a normalization of the inputs is not necessary, which is recommended by us in particular for the computation of view factors. The non-existing possibility of RFRs to extrapolate may be limiting at first sight. At second sight, it prevents the prediction of completely unphysical values, which could be dangerous in complex particle simulations. Of course, it requires a very carefully composed training data set, but this is true for regression models in general.

In summary, we have extended the use of pre-trained Machine Learning-based models from monodisperse to polydisperse systems. These models are now available for usage in DEM and CFD-DEM-based simulations. Further steps can be made either towards even more detailed simulations in terms of particle shape considerations or towards application in industrial-sized process simulations. For the latter, an interesting detail would be to minimize the computational cost for radiation modeling in situations with high particle dynamics, i.e., a fast re-arrangement of particles.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Marker definitions

Table A1 gives an overview of all particle–particle interaction markers and their definitions. All definitions of non-interaction markers for particle–particle as well as for particle–wall interactions are summarized in Table A2. Table A3 summarizes all particle–wall interaction markers and their definitions.

Appendix B. Monte Carlo Integration

To calculate the local particle volume fraction in a cubic mesh grid $\varphi_{p,c}$, random values between zero and one are generated in the direction of each coordinate. The random values represent a continuous uniform distribution. The values are then scaled to the respective cube size and shifted to the desired cube origin. Integration is then performed by determining the proportion of points generated within a particle and the total number of points generated. To reduce the computational cost, particles farther from the cube center than the cube diagonal plus the maximum particle radius are not considered in the integration. In order to correctly determine the local particle fractions near the boundaries, 26 periodic images of the original particle bed are created and placed around the original simulation box to form a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ cube. Particle volume fractions are determined with 20,000 points per cube.

Exemplarily shown in Fig. B1, we performed the MC integration of the unit circle, which corresponds to the 2D counterpart of the DEM-based particle positions. When using 3000 points the error is 0.178%.

Appendix C1. Three marker particle–particle models trained with transformed target

Fig. C1 shows all predictions of three marker models trained with transformed targets for particle–particle interaction.

Appendix C2. Four marker particle–particle models trained with transformed target

Fig. C2 shows all four marker model predictions, when trained with transformed targets for particle–particle interaction.

Appendix D1. Three marker particle–wall models trained with transformed target

In Fig. D1 all predictions of three marker models trained with transformed targets for particle–wall interaction are shown.

Appendix D2. Four marker particle–wall models trained with transformed target

Fig. D2 displays all predictions of four marker models trained with transformed targets for particle–wall interaction.

Appendix E. Computational cost

The number of training data samples is 4,794,535, and the number of test data samples is 599,345. In Table E1, the training duration is the average time a single combination in the randomized search took, using stratified k-fold cross-validation with the number of k-fold is equal to five. The evaluation time includes renormalization and thresholding of the model predictions. One

has to note that loading and evaluation were performed on a single thread, while training was performed using four parallel threads. All times here are measured in Python®.

As can be seen, the training times of the DNN are significantly higher than those of the RFR or the XGB model. However, the training time strongly depends on the number of epochs, e.g., the average training time for random combinations with 25 epochs is 85.5 min compared to 602.5 min for 200 epochs. The ensemble of DNNs requires the longest training time, the training of the level 0 models needs 39.27 (min) and, as mentioned, is strongly dependent on the number of epochs. The final training of the level 1 model then takes 311.8 (min). The XGB model is by far the fastest overall. The RFR requires significantly less training effort and less evaluation time than the DNN, but loading the model takes the longest. Since the model loading would take place in the initialization of a simulation, a long duration is not a criterion for exclusion.

In our previous work (Tausendschön & Radl, 2021), the first DEM loop took 3.011 (s). This time includes the loading of the DNN, the marker calculation, the view factor calculation, and the heat transfer calculation. The marker calculation itself took 3 (s). The times were measured for two marker DNNs with a single hidden layer containing 150 hidden nodes.

For comparison, we created four marker DNNs with one hidden layer containing 150 hidden nodes. The time needed for the same DEM loop in the same particle bed is 3.484 (s). The marker calculation time is now 3.469 (s). As can be seen, the increase in simulation time is around 15%.

Appendix F. Supplementary material

All trained and used Machine Learning models using four markers, except the RFRs, can be downloaded in the “Supplementary Material” of the online version. The RFRs can be downloaded here <https://cloud.tugraz.at/index.php/s/q9FymHBKxWQ7icY>.

Appendix G. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2022.05.011>.

Fig. B1. Example Monte Carlo integration of unit circle.

Fig. C1. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle–particle dataset of three marker models trained with transformed targets.

Fig. C2. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle–particle dataset of four marker models trained with transformed targets.

Fig. D1. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle–wall dataset of three marker models trained with transformed targets.

Fig. D2. Comparison of the predictions on the total particle–wall dataset of four marker models trained with transformed targets.

Table A1

Overview of the investigated interaction markers for particle–particle interaction and their definitions.

Marker particle–particle	Definition
$\frac{1}{ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} }$	$((x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2 + (z_i - z_j)^2)^{-1/2}$
$\frac{r_j}{ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} }$	$\frac{r_j}{ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} }; \frac{r_{eff}}{ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} }; \frac{r_i}{ \mathbf{x}_{i-j} }$
$\frac{r_j}{r_i}$	
$n_{pib,i-j,r_i}$	Based on Eqs. (3)–(5), with $r_{search} = r_i$
$n_{pib,i-j,r_j}$	Based on Eqs. (3)–(5), with $r_{search} = r_j$
$n_{pib,i-j,r_{max}}$	Based on Eqs. (3)–(5), with $r_{search} = r_{max}$
$n_{pib,i-j,r_{ij,max}}$	Based on Eqs. (3)–(5), with $r_{search} = r_{ij,max}$
$n_{pib,i-j,TC}$	Based on Eqs. (3)–(8)

Table A2

Overview of all non-interaction markers applied to particle–particle and particle–wall interactions.

Marker	Definition
n_{piS}	Based on Eq. (9), with $r_{search} = 2 r_{max}$
$\phi_{p,sys}$	
$\phi_{p,r_{min}}$	
$\phi_{p,r_{max}}$	
$\phi_{p,S}$	$\sum_{i \in S_i} \frac{V_{seg,p,i}}{V_{sphere}}$
$\phi_{p,C}$	See Appendix A

Table A3

Overview of the investigated interaction markers for particle–wall interaction and their definitions.

Marker particle–wall	Definition
$\frac{1}{ n_{wall-i} }$	$\frac{1}{ x_{wall-i} n n_{wall} }$
$\frac{r_i}{ n_{wall-i} }$	$\frac{r_i}{ x_{wall-i} n n_{wall} }$
$\frac{A_i}{A_{wall}}$	$\frac{4 \pi r_i^2}{l_{wall}^2}$
$n_{pib,wall-i,r_i}$	Based on Eqs. (3)–(5), with $r_{search} = r_i$
$n_{pib,wall-i,r_{max}}$	Based on Eqs. (3)–(5), with $r_{search} = r_{max}$

Table E1

Training-, loading- and evaluation time overview.

Model	Training duration (min)	Model loading (s)	Evaluation time test dataset (s)
DNN	315.3	0.1975	9.587
RFR	22.23	2.887	4.816
XGB	1.341	0.0104	0.6321
eDNN	351.1	0.6990	25.16

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